

THE ROLE OF ADVANCED PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE QUALITY ORGANIZATION OF THE PROCESS OF MUSIC EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article discusses the scientific-theoretical importance of using innovative advanced pedagogical technologies in organizing the teaching process of "Music Education" in a way that meets the requirements.

Key words: Music education, educational system, educational technology, method-style, science, interactive method.

INTRODUCTION.

Along with updating and improving the content of education and increasing the quality indicators, it is necessary to improve the qualifications of teachers-trainers, to keep them in step with the development of science and science, especially those who can effectively use information technologies and interactive methods, which are widely used in all fields. One of the important tasks of today is training (re-training) to the level of being able to freely communicate with the computer and to be able to apply it in one's work to ensure the effectiveness of the lesson.

The study, observation and analysis of practical experiences in the application of pedagogical technologies to education show that the organization of training on the basis of interactive methods is becoming widespread in almost all stages of education. In our opinion, this should not lead to the conclusion that one or another type of pedagogical technology should be used in every lesson. When the advanced pedagogical technology is effective, it is interesting for students, it can direct them to active, independent and creative thinking and observation.

For this purpose, the teacher should choose the pedagogical technology taking into account the lesson topic, structure, students' interest, and if there are music lessons, they should use them taking into account the theoretical, practical, performance possibilities.

The main goals and objectives of the use of pedagogical technologies include the following: Organization, working in cooperation (teacher-student interaction), group and individual work, each lesson ensuring student activity, improving, analyzing, comparing, summarizing, drawing conclusions, controlling, evaluating, etc.

In the process of teaching subjects, it is appropriate for every teacher to work according to the following preparation system for using pedagogical technologies:

- ◆ Defining the topic;
- ◆ Setting the goal correctly;
- ◆ Determining key words that should be mastered on the topic;
- ◆ Tasks 1,2,3,4.... determine;
- ◆ Creation of technological process scenario;
- ◆ Individual performance;
- ◆ Working as a group (small group) and team;
- ◆ Q&A with the whole team, discussion, cluster, brainstorming and more.

- ◆ Regulations;
- ◆ Assessment;
- ◆ Conclusion;

Ready-made technologies that have been tested and have had positive (high) results are applied to the educational process. Currently, attention is being paid to the design of educational activities and the use of technologies specific to certain subjects. A similar situation can be seen in the experience of technologyization of music lessons. As an example of this, technologies such as "Concert lessons", "Quiz lessons", "Fun and clever lessons", "Musical journey", "I am a conductor" used by advanced pedagogues can be shown. What is meant by training design and what is it based on? Below we present the stages of organizing the training process based on design:

Collecting materials related to the subject of the lesson (Teacher's preparation on the subject);

Determining the purpose and tasks of studying the subject;

Choosing the type, form, methods and tools of the lesson;

Taking into account the amount of time spent in the process of mastering the concept, knowledge, skills, and abilities provided for in the project (for example, planning the amount of time allocated to each activity in music lessons);

Exercises, examples that form the basis of the results achieved at each stage (assignment, practical demonstration);

Organizational structure and conclusion of the training, conclusions;

Regardless of the part of the lesson, its type (lecture, practical, seminar, and singing, listening to music, music literacy in music lessons), the students' psychological and physiological characteristics, levels of preparation (voice range), singing opportunities, age characteristics) should be taken into account. In this process, the main focus is on increasing the activity of students, teaching them to think independently, to think creatively, to develop executive skills, to work according to their needs and interests, to use their internal capabilities and talents, should be focused on developing the skills of self-control and independent learning.

Here we will focus on the remarkable features of the application of advanced pedagogical technologies to the educational environment:

When learning any subject, students are not only taught, they are taught to study independently;

The knowledge and concepts given to the students are not given ready-made, but the students are taught to collect and study the information and information related to the topic independently using the sources;

Skills for working with curriculum, textbooks, manuals, lecture texts are formed;

The student is trained to be able to express, defend and prove his opinion;

Currently, in all the educational system of our republic, especially in the system of higher pedagogical education, great importance is attached to raising the quality and efficiency of teacher training, and various pedagogical researches are being conducted in this regard. Most of these researches are aimed at increasing the effectiveness of education by introducing advanced pedagogical technologies in order to achieve the goal of education and its high results, and technologyization of education is one of the most important tasks. A teacher's high pedagogical skills and level of knowledge are undoubtedly one of the important factors of education. An experienced teacher with high pedagogical skills does not simply explain the

lesson. If we explain this on the example of music lessons, the teacher's speech skills, playing a musical instrument, singing, using various visual and technical tools play a big role in making the lesson interesting and meaningful. .

In music lessons, most of the students sing in imitation of the teacher, follow him, follow his example, the personal "example" of the teacher is important. Because practical performance takes the leading place in the lesson, no goal can be achieved with a dry narrative style. Carefully organized scientific and pedagogical training is one of the main factors that ensure the effectiveness of education. The teachers actively participating in this process regularly improve their pedagogical skills and serve as an example to others in ensuring the effectiveness of education and training, in bringing up a competent generation responsible for the future. Therefore, it is possible to achieve good results by constantly improving and encouraging the innovative activities and experiences of advanced pedagogues who conduct "Music culture" lessons at every level of education, including general education schools.

In connection with the organization of innovative activity on a scientific basis, the most important thing in the introduction of advanced pedagogical technologies to the educational process is to take into account the readiness and interest of students in this activity and to choose the necessary technology. whether it is a school, college or university, the main goal of an educational institution is to impart knowledge to a pupil or student. In addition to imparting knowledge, the teacher looks for the most convenient and effective ways of imparting knowledge and organizes the educational process in an interesting and meaningful way. Such activity itself can be called educational technology. Educational technology (from the Greek "tekhne" - skill, art, "logos" - means understanding, teaching) or pedagogical technology, introducing various ways and methods of pedagogical education into one's activity at the same time, it is necessary to make sure that this process will give results.

Important situations and situations in determining the process of pedagogical training for pedagogical technology: preliminary determination of the tasks that a pupil or student will face in the process of learning, the content of education at each stage of education (curriculum, program, essence of the subject, o determining the availability of educational and methodological resources, determining knowledge and concepts, their degree of complexity and degree of compatibility with the student's knowledge and skills, education and training forms and tools (additional resources, question-and-answer, discussion, test preparation of questions, demonstrations, hearing using technical means, listening resources); Pedagogical technologies, such as planning the tasks assigned to the student in class and outside of class for the objective assessment of the student's acquired knowledge and skills in accordance with the criteria for evaluating the quality of the educational result and mastery level.

It is necessary to pay attention to the following in order to prepare future teachers for pedagogical activities in higher educational institutions of pedagogy:

To study the experiences of new and effective work secrets of teachers operating on the basis of a technological approach;

To increase the activity of pedagogues in the technological approach and, on the contrary, to identify the causes of the problems hindering it, to search for more effective ways of working based on the technological approach;

To learn the unique methods of advanced pedagogical technologies of experienced teachers, identifying their differences and similarities, their shortcomings and achievements, and applying them in their work.

So, pedagogical technology is a method of education, in a certain sense, a set of educational processes, tools, forms and methods. Selection of educational materials, reworking, changing the form and size of the subject according to the specific structure of the subject, the ability of the students, the level of mastery of the subject is also related to the educational technology. The fact that the teacher organizes the educational process on the basis of technological methods largely depends on him, his knowledge and familiarity with the organizational structure of each of them is an important guarantee of ensuring the effectiveness of education. The teacher should be well aware of the knowledge related to the meaningful and effective organization of pedagogical technologies in the application of them, be able to evaluate the positive effects of the used technologies on the effectiveness of the lesson and analyze the results, be able to draw appropriate conclusions, and have a critical attitude to their own activities. It is important to be able to connect students' active participation in the lesson by connecting their own knowledge with practical activities. Therefore, it is necessary for all science teachers, including music teachers, to be well aware of advanced interactive technologies. Because the content, goals and tasks of education are expanding as a result of the development of science. In this process, the forms and methods of teaching are improving. As a result, the main directions of human activity, i.e. education and training in the educational system, are turning into a holistic system, i.e. technologies, which provide opportunities for the full realization of the intended goals.

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